

Assessment of Administration, Planning and Supervision among Government Secondary School Principals in Dala Educational Zone of Kano State

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Abstract

This paper assessed administration, planning and supervision among government secondary school principals in Dala educational zone of Kano State. Three objectives and corresponding research questions guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all public secondary school Principals in Dala Educational zone, during the 2022/2023 academic session. 55 (35 Male and 20 Female) principals constitute the sample size of the size, this was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.741 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The conclusion was made as effective motivation and supervision of educational and planning is necessary for good outcomes of secondary schools. The recommendations Government should provide periodic training, seminars, and workshops on planning for principals.

Keywords: Administration, Supervision, Educational, Planning, Principals.

Introduction

Educational institutions including Secondary Schools are designed to achieve specific goal of preparing individuals as good and responsible citizens. Olajide (2016) asserted that principals are key administrators in secondary schools through whom their competencies would influence teachers to achieve secondary educational goals. Principals could play their roles effectively towards the attainment of the objectives of secondary schools when they possess the requisite competencies, leadership, talents, administrative efficiency, managerial skills, planning skills and the competency to motivate teachers to pursue such effort, which could help in achieving stated secondary educational goals. As an administrator, every principal is expected to provide professional guidance to teachers in order to improve the conditions which affect learning and growth of students and teachers. In discharging their administrative roles, principals may help teachers to perform their jobs in preparing lesson plans; good use of instructional materials or aids, keeping and maintaining of school records, provision of required instructional materials to teachers among others (Fika, Ibi & Aji 2015). Educational planning is an element of the educational and leadership management in educational institutions that includes ambition of general and specific objectives and priorities from educational strategies and existing resources to predict the future of different circumstances. This is corroborated by DeMathers et al, (2020) who argued that the main beliefs, values, knowledge, teaching and educational management practices by the school administration reflect their educational effects and the outcome on tis educational institutions (Kaufman, 2020). Nwabueze, (2016) is of the view that the principals provide good leadership for proper direction and effective coordination with the school to develop and maintain effective educational administration and Planning programmes and promote the improvement of teaching and learning in the school. The principals have the responsibilities for the organization of the school, development of instructional programme, assigned of duties to members of their staff, general operation of the school facilities and whole school supervision (Wallace Foundation (2013). The role of the secondary school principal has changed dramatically over the past two decades. Once seen primarily as instructional leaders, principals are now increasingly being viewed as government agents, responsible for implementing government policies and agendas. This shift has been driven by a number of factors, including the rise of standardized testing, the increasing focus on accountability, and the growing emphasis on school choice. As a result of these changes, principals are facing a number of challenges, including balancing the demands of multiple stakeholders, managing an increasingly complex bureaucracy, and maintaining a focus on student learning amidst competing priorities (McKenna, 2018).

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Education deals with knowledge acquisition, training and development of the individual to be able to contribute positively. Education embraces not only school experiences but also indirect or incidental influences which help us to learn, which activities affect our characters, behaviors and perceptions. Ogunode, (2020) sees education as an enabling agency by which Africans could restore their self-confidence, and make those who doubted the humanity of Africans begin to revise their views and learn to respect Africans. From the above education is a form of training given to the individual that makes him useful in the communities. Administration has an infinitive form to administer, which means to manage. It also derives from the Dutch Language “administratie” which meaning ranges from administration to management of organizational activities. Some experts provide definitions for the term. Administration is the overall determination of policies, setting of major objectives, identification of general purposes, and laying down of broad programs and project. Administration is the guidance, leadership and control of the efforts of the groups towards some common goals. <https://www.hashmicro.com>.

Educational administration is a process that includes the combined operation through which a country is maintained in good working conditions. It is a process of utilizing appropriate material in such a way as to promote effectively the development of human qualities. It includes all those techniques and procedures employed in operating the educational organization in accordance with established policies. It is the totality of resources which are made available and made effective for accomplishing the purpose of an enterprise. Educational administration includes functions like planning, organizing, financing, directing, supervising, inspecting and evaluation. It is also concerned with elements like setting up of goals of education, review, feedback and innovations (wordpress.com). Nwankwoala, (2016) defines the term as a broad umbrella encompassing a number of processes such as planning, coordinating, controlling, and being involved in other management processes and contribute to formulation of policies. In order, to achieve these goals, the head of the educational organization plans carefully various programmes and activities. The educational organization may be a school, college or university. The head organizes these programmes and activities with cooperation from other teachers, parents, and students, motivating them and coordinating the efforts of staff members as well as directing and exercising control over them. The head evaluates the performance and progress of staff in achieving the purpose of educational programme, provides feedback to them and brings modification in the plans and programmes of the institution when required. The totality of these processes, which are directed towards realizing or achieving the purposes of the school is called educational administration.

Planning is considered one the basic processes that emphasis importance in improving the policies, ways, and means, which are organized to choose the best possible solutions to reach certain objectives in light of the different organizational resources. Orefice and Guraziu (2018). The concept of educational planning has developed within a comprehensive framework of steps, procedures and methods used to achieve these objectives and to ensure the degree of achievement of the objectives in the process comprehensive pre-vision of all the elements of the educational process Ismail et al, (2021). And it was not on a specific aspect of the educational process but rather it concerned with the educational aspects in the educational institutions. Yemini et al, (2018). Furthermore, it is applied to education at all levels and its forms and stages, regular and non-formal and addresses the categories of society in educational institutions, educational circular, effective teaching methods, teacher preparation, technological means and others. Aderonum, et al. (2021) defined educational Administration as “essentially a service, activity or which the fundamental objectives of the education process may be more fully and efficiently realized. Educational administration broadly means running of education institutions, which involves guidance, leadership and controlling of the efforts of individuals in the achievement of the goals of the institutions. Okoroma (2016), outline the objectives of educational administration are as to provide proper education to students to ensure adequate utilization of all resources; ensure professional ethnics and professional development among teachers; organize educational programmes for acquainting students with the art of democratic citizenship; mobilize the community; organize co-curricular activities effectively for developing talents of students and work efficiency of educational teachers. He further stated to include get the work done; prepare students for taking their places in vocations and of life and train the students in developing scientific attitude and objectives outwork among them towards all aspects and activities of life and to ensure quantitative improvement of education. Motivation is an internal process. Maslow stated (Sutrisno and Sunarsi, 2019) that the motivation is to create the driving force behind the stimulation of work to collaborate, work effectively, and integrate into their job satisfaction efforts. However, Matsso and Dahlqvist (2013), assert that motivation is an essential tool for improving and retaining employee performance in Dala Educational Zone, Kano State.

Educational Administration and Planning of Principals activities are very paramount importance in the secondary school education, which requires adequate planning by the principals for the improvement of quality assurance which lead to the attainment of educational goals/objectives including academic excellence, discipline, high enrolment, good administration and excellence outcome of the school results. Therefore, lack of effectiveness of supervision by principals such as regular

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lesson plan check as well as scheme of works, lack of monitoring of staff activities, lack of observing teachers attitudes, mentoring teachers on modern teaching methods and facilities, lack of incentives for those who observed, lack of regular training, workshop and seminars, lack of adequate training and resources: Many principals in Dala Educational Zone lack the necessary training and resources to effectively administer, plan, and supervise their schools. This can lead to a number of problems, including ineffective leadership, poor decision-making, lack of accountability, poor communication: There is often a lack of communication between principals and their staff. A lack of trust, lack of collaboration, lack of shared goals in effective use of data: Principals often do not effectively use data to inform their decisions. Poor resource allocation, ineffective interventions, lack of progress Low morale: There is often low morale among teachers in Dala Educational Zone. This can be due to a number of factors, including poor leadership, low pay, lack of resources, High turnover: There is a high turnover rate of principals in Dala Educational Zone. This can lead to: lack of continuity, lack of institutional knowledge, lack of stability by the principals are the major problems that study needs to overcome. In line with the above, this paper intends to assess administration, planning and supervision among Government Secondary School principals in Dala educational Zone of Kano State.

Objective of the Study

The aim of the research is to assess administration, planning and supervision among Government Secondary School principals in Dala Educational Zone of Kano State and the specific objectives are as follows;

1. Determine the extent of supervision on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State.
2. Determine the extent of motivation on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala zone of Kano State.
3. Determine the extent of interpersonal influence on improving administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of supervision on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?
2. What is the extent of interpersonal influence on improving administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?
3. What is the extent of interpersonal influence on improving administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all public secondary school Principals in Dala Educational zone, during the 2022/2023 academic session. 55 (35 Male and 20 Female) principals constitute the sample size of the study, this was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument of data collection was structured questionnaire which was validated by 3 experts. The instrument was validated and reliability coefficient of 0.741 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. The data collected for this study were coded into statistical package of social sciences (SPSS), 25.0. The package was used to calculate mean and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the extent of supervision on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?

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Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Influence of Supervision on Principal Administration and Planning in Dala Educational zone of Kano State, Nigeria?

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	The principal supervises instructional activities to improve teacher's competencies	88	3.58	1.251	Agreed
2	The principal supervision improves identification of areas of strength and weakness.	88	3.75	1.215	Agreed
3	The supervision provides adequate control measure and properly established by principals.	88	3.47	1.219	Agreed
4	The supervision help in avoiding wrong decision and mistake from the teachers.	88	3.76	1.238	Agreed
5	The principal supervision improves teachers' self-confidence and ability to perform duties effectively.	88	3.62	1.234	Agreed
6	The supervision improves decision making process.	88	3.73	1.173	Agreed
7	The supervision upgrades the level of performance of subordinate.	88	3.58	1.126	Agreed
8	The supervision helps in analysis of problems and skillful use of logic and good judgment.	88	3.66	1.234	Agreed
GRAND TOTAL			3.64		

Source: Field Study 2023.

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in table 1 revealed that all items of the variable of Influence of Supervision on Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria were having a mean score of above 3.0. The mean scores of secretarial professions ranging from 3.47 to 3.58. The grand mean of supervision on improving school administration is 3.63 which is above the benchmark of revised four-point Likert scale. The results indicated that the respondents agreed with statements that supervision influence the performance of Principals administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What is the extent of motivation on improving secondary school administration among principals in Dala zone of Kano State?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Influence of Motivation on Principal Administration and Planning in Dala Educational zone of Kano State, Nigeria?

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	Stimulating and providing guidance by the principal display improve the school administration.	88	3.59	1.222	Agreed
2	The principal encourage the staff by encouraging their effort.	88	3.48	1.303	Agreed
3	The exchanging ideas and opportunity arouse teaching and no teaching attention.	88	3.69	1.190	Agreed
4	Without tangible reinforcement staff cannot charge their duties at the right time.	88	3.74	1.121	Agreed
5	Reward and punishment are the measure for improving school administration by the principals.	88	3.70	1.991	Agreed
6	The division of labor by the principal improve the quality of leadership in the school	88	3.69	1.269	Agreed
7	It was too easy to share my decision content with subordinate in order to improve the leadership.	88	1.32	1.032	Disagreed
8	The principal felt control of the leadership style in the school	88	3.69	1.269	Agreed
GRAND TOTAL			3.36		

Source: Field Study 2023

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in Table 2 indicates that only one items of the variable on the influence of Motivation on Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria disagreed with mean score of 1.32,

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while other items agreed were having a mean score of above 3.0, the mean scores of motivations on improving principal administration ranging from 1.32 to 3.74. The grand mean of motivation on improving principal administration is 3.36 which are above the benchmark of revised four-point Likert scale. The result indicates that the respondents agreed with statements of Influence of Motivation in Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Question 3

What is the extent of interpersonal influence on improving administration among principals in Dala Educational zone of Kano State?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Influence of Interpersonal skills on Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria?

S/N	ITEMS	N	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1	Good planning improves level of positive relationship among the staff.	88	3.48	1.219	Agreed
2	The duties assign to staff create room for good relationship between staff and principals	88	3.68	1.189	Agreed
3	The principal is responsible for improving healthy relationship between staff in the schools	88	3.63	1.217	Agreed
4	Friendly and responsible relationship improve good administration by the principal.	88	3.14	1.333	Agreed
5	The principal is responsible for an attending staff improve complain improve the school administration.	88	3.29	1.297	Agreed
6	Maintaining temper and remain cool even in chaos situation improve principal administration.	88	3.68	1.248	Agreed
7	The frequent get together with subordinates improve the principal administrations.	88	3.62	1.336	Agreed
8	The team work is element of improving principals' administration in the school	88	3.70	1.991	Agreed
GRAND TOTAL			3.38		

Source: Field Study 2023

The output of the descriptive statistics presented in Table 3 indicates that all items of the variable on the of Influence of Interpersonal skills on Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria agreed were having a mean score of above 3.0, the mean scores of Interpersonal skills on Improving Principal Administration in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria relevancy of secretarial profession in public institution ranging from 3.13 to 3.68. The grand mean of interpersonal skills is 3.07 which are above the benchmark of revised four-point Likert scale. The results indicated that the respondents agreed with statements of interpersonal skills improving principal administration.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question 1 indicate that the respondents agreed with statements of Influence of Motivation and Supervision on Principal Administration and Planning in Dala Educational Zone of Kano State, Nigeria. This is in line with finding that there are effective principal's supervisory roles that encourage teacher's job performance. Nakpodia (2011) who noted that teacher's performance in Secondary schools is significantly dependent on the capacity of the principals effectively conduct adequate and valuable supervision which validates the importance of discipline, record keeping and teaching aids. Supervision refers to the activities that are directed towards improving the conditions sounding the growth of the students and teachers. The role of principals as a supervisor is to improve, encourage, coordinate and direct teachers towards personal and institutional goal attainment. Supervision of teachers by principals is a prerequisite to enhance professional standard in teaching profession.

The findings of research question 2 revealed that respondents agreed with statements of Influence of Motivation on Principal Administration and Planning in Dala zone of Kano State, Nigeria. This is in line with findings of there are lack of motivation of teachers on secondary schools' administration and planning in Dala educational zone of Kano state by encouraging poor planning on record keeping, causing poor planning of periodic workshops and conferences in schools. This

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brings hazy preparation of budget, causes poor teaching, because of poor teaching plan, breeds role conflict amongst staff, causes inadequate and poor facilities and instructional materials, there are school insecurity, poor maintenance of equipment, poor educational administration and planning of extracurricular activities and leads to poor classroom supervision. This is in line with Ikediugwu and Chukwumah (2015) who stated that probably the reason for poor infrastructure, inadequate staffing, inadequate funding and poor-quality assurance owing to various training limitation could be adduced to poor strategic management skills of the principals who have not dutifully motivated to put things in place. Therefore, poor educational administration and planning breeds mismanagement and mal administration in secondary schools. Principals should try as much as possible to see that effective and proper training and motivation is carried out in the schools to avoid all these negative influences on their schools.

The finding of the research question 3 indicates that that the respondents agreed with statements interpersonal skills on principal administration and planning. This in line with Mustapha (2019) and Wang Pollock and Hausemen (2019), whose findings rated principal's interpersonal relationship at the most important source of the principal administration. This corroborates Di Benneto and Afered (2017), who arrived within the school community is a crucial determinant of attainment of educational goals and principal's administration. This means that a positive interpersonal relationship fosters not only principal's administration but in their entire life.

Conclusion

The successful administration, planning and supervision among government secondary school principals in Dala educational zone of Kano state that the provision of necessary regular training, and working materials should be provided by the government. Encourage principals to use data to inform their decisions and the government review that teachers' salaries and allowance for effective administration to take place. An effective educational and planning is necessary for good outcomes of secondary schools. Practicing good administration and planning in schools helps in maximizing fund resources, human and material resources to meet the demands of education in order to achieve the desired goals with the given time. Also, good administration planning is required to get full cooperation of staff in the schools and the need to change, improve and adapt the educational system to suit our needs. With all these things in place, good school administration is guaranteed. Provide principals with the necessary training and resources: Principals need to be trained in effective leadership, decision-making, and data analysis. They also need to be provided with the resources they need to do their jobs effectively. Improve communication between principals and their staff: Principals need to establish open and honest communication with their staff. This can be done through regular meetings, one-on-one conversations, and surveys. Address the factors that contribute to low morale among teachers: Principals need to create a positive and supportive work environment for their staff. They also need to advocate for better pay and resources for teachers. Take steps to reduce principal turnover: Principals need to be given the support they need to be successful in their roles. This includes providing them with training, mentorship, and resources.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should provide periodic training, seminars, and workshops on planning for principals.
2. Government should place experience and high level of education as conditions for principal ship. This will improve successful administration and planning in schools.
3. Principals should have to establish interpersonal relationship to teachers and good communication skills in their schools.
4. Government should provide adequate funds to secondary schools to enable principals engage comfortably in the administrative responsibilities.

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